
FOREIGN CAPITAL INFLOWS AND ECONOMIC GROWTH NEXUS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between foreign capital inflows and economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1981 to 2023. Specifically, the study investigated the extent to which foreign capital flows through foreign direct investment, foreign portfolio investment, external debt stock and foreign aids influences gross domestic product proxy for economic growth in Nigeria, using secondary data from Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and World Bank global data base. Descriptive statistics, Unit root test, Johanson co-integration test and Error correction model were employed to analyze the data. The Johanson co-integration test revealed the presence of long run relationship among variables. The short run dynamics test showed that, previous year foreign direct investment exhibits strong but negative influence on gross domestic product for the period, foreign portfolio investment is positive but weak while external debt stock and foreign aids exhibit weak negative impacts on gross domestic products. The study thus, concluded that foreign direct investment is a significant predictor of economic growth in Nigeria and recommends that, the managers of the Nigerian economy should consider restructuring economic policies on foreign direct investment with the aim of increasing investment inflows that is capable of improving the value of domestic production, leading to high productive capacity. Efforts should be made to deliberately channel borrowed funds to target productive economic activities that are capable of increasing the productive capacity of the economy. Also, pro-active financial control measures should be set in place to stop diversion of funds from productive sectors to non-productive sectors of the economy.

Keywords: Foreign Direct Investment, Co-integration, Economic Growth

1. Introduction

Foreign capital flows to a developing economy is vital for stimulating growth and development of any nation of the world. Nigeria as a developing country deserves to embrace opportunities that are capable of maximizing economic outputs, growth and development. Economic growth is one macro-economic objective desired by developing countries of the world, including the Nigeria economy. Isibor, Omorose and Ahmed (2024) noted that if the economy of a nation is open and opportunities to diversify investment are provided to investors, risk inherent in asset investments will be minimized. He explained further, that in addition to internal phenomenon like domestic savings and investment, capital flows from foreign investment and other external sources can contribute to a greater extent to growth and development of developing nations. Yahuza baba and Afroz (2023) also emphasized that foreign capital flows to developing countries are potential drivers of economic growth and development. Foreign capital inflows in the nature of direct and portfolio investment to specific sectors of the economy are expected to supplement domestic savings and investment, increase technological base, reduce unemployment rate, upgrade innovations, expand capital formation and contribute to correction of adverse balance of payment. Onwuteaka (2023) asserted that, the improvement of human development is increased by foreign direct investment and foreign direct investment flows to developing economy has significant effect on infrastructural development as well as economic growth. Due to maximum benefits attributed to foreign capital flows to domestic countries, most developing countries grant incentives as strategies to attract greater percentages. However, the volatility and dependency of foreign capital inflows can pose significant risks to an economy, particularly in the face of global financial uncertainties. The controversy in existing literature of whether foreign capital inflows significantly affect economic growth in Nigeria (Okoro, Nzotta & Alajekwu, 2020; Uwubanmwun & Ogiemudia, 2016; Fredrick, 2019) or do not have significant effects on economic growth in Nigeria (Ajaji, Anifowose & Ekwere, 2023; Kisito & Hooi, 2019) necessitate this study. Therefore, this study demands critical re-examination of whether foreign capital inflows influence economic growth in Nigeria or not, using four basic indicators of foreign capital inflows (foreign direct investment, foreign portfolio investment, external debt stock and foreign aids) as the explanatory variables to test their relationship with gross domestic product which is absorbed as the explained variable, proxy for economic growth in Nigeria. The period of study for this research work is extended to a period of 42 years, from 1981 to 2023 so as to understand better, the long run effect of foreign capital inflows on economic growth in Nigeria.

2. Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

Concept of Economic Growth Economic growth – Economic growth is an important objective of macroeconomic policy described as the process where the real per capital income of a country increases over a long period of time and is measured by the increase in the amount of goods and services produced in a country (Jhingan, 2013). Sanusi (2011) viewed economic growth as an increase in a nation's goods and services which arises as a result of increase in economic activities that take place over a period of time. A prolonged increase in a nation's gross domestic products (GDP) contributes significantly to speedy growth and development of any nation of the world, including the Nigeria economy. As the nation's gross domestic products increases, national income is bound to increase but where a nation's gross domestic products diminish or fluctuates over time, such an economy will find it difficult to grow and develop. One major impact of long-term growth of a country is that it has positive impact on national income and the level of employment which increases the

standard of living of citizens. As a country's gross domestic products increases, it leads to more people getting job and as employment rate increases, income also increases and has a multiplier effect on citizen's per capita income and welfare. When national output expands, national income also increases and economic wealth multiplies. Higher economic growth leads to extra tax income for government spending, increasing investment by investors leads to more profit which is capable of increasing tax revenue for economic development purposes. Okonkwo et al (2023) explains that economic growth should be expected to follow a pattern consistent with government capital expenditures on administration, social and community service, transfers and government deficits. He further explained that long term character of capital investment which result in the formation of assets, enables the economy to generate income for many years by expanding and upgrading manufacturing facilities and increasing operational effectiveness. Concept of Foreign Capital Inflows Foreign capital inflow is the total monetary value of financial resources received by a country from other countries through direct investments, portfolio investments, external borrowing, aids, remittances etc.

Onwuteaka, et al. (2023) reported that, from the inception of political independence in most of the West African nations, inflows of external capital in nature of foreign investment and multinational firms' operations have been partly useful in accessing economic performance of member countries and that records from the Central Bank of Nigerian statistical bulletin of 2021 provided an evidence to assert that the quantum of external capital inflows into the Nigerian economy have increased over the years due to the standardization of the Nigerian capital market. The inflows penetrated into the Nigerian nation in the form of foreign direct investment, foreign portfolio investment, foreign aids, multilateral and bilateral trade etc.

However, the ability of the economy to put these amounts into productive use determines the extent to which it can impact growth and development of the nation. Chiamaka et al, (2023) viewed the importance of foreign capitals to the Nigeria economy and concluded that foreign capital inflows in form of foreign portfolio investment has the capability of increasing growth in the Nigerian economy. Investments in bonds, stocks, mutual funds, global depositary receipt etc. requires no direct control and management but increases investment opportunities in financial assets/ securities by foreign investors. It serves as an important source of capital flows to domestic economies and has the capability of increasing the liquidity position of domestic capital market which helps to develop market efficiency. Foreign capital inflows in form of foreign direct investment and foreign portfolio investment to an economy is determined by different factors including foreign exchange rate of investor's nation and the recipient economy. These form of investment inflows to developing nations, including efficient usage of external debt and foreign aids in form of foreign development assistance to a developing economy can supplement domestic savings and investment, increase technological base, reduce unemployment rate, upgrades innovations, expand capital formation and contribute to correction of adverse balance of payment.

Theoretical Framework

This research work is anchored on: Two gap hypothesis. Two gap hypothesis developed by Chenery and Strout in 1966 explains the importance of foreign capital flows to less developed countries. The theory posits that, inflows of foreign capitals to less developed countries has the ability to promote faster growth and development by bridging the funding gaps created by trade imbalances and poor domestic savings and investment, that savings and investment accumulated by developing economies may not be sufficient to enhanced quick economic growth, thus the need for less developed countries to improves their capitals by accessing foreign investment and foreign aids necessary for faster growth and development. The theory

explains further that, gaps created by insufficient savings/ investment and foreign exchange shortage created by low net export earnings of less developed countries can hinder targeted rate of economic growth and that foreign capital flows through aids and investment can be useful to meet the country's specified foreign exchange requirement necessary to fill existing gaps and ascertain growth and development (Akarara & Ouseibai, 2022)

Empirical Review

Several scholars in their studies have tried to relate foreign capital inflows to economic growth (Ajayi, Anifowose, & Ekwere, 2023; Bashir, 2024; Obodoechi, et al 2022: and Ezeaku, et al 2020). Widening this discussion is the study conducted by Oniore, Ogwuche and Audu (2024) when they examined the impact of foreign capital inflows on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1986 to 2023. Foreign direct investment, personal remittances, official development assistance and external debt stock were examined as the explanatory variables to check their effects on gross domestic products proxy for economic growth as the explained variable. The study employed modified ordinary least square regression method of analysis to analyze the data. The test results revealed that FDI was significant but has negative association with GDP. ODA was insignificant but positive; EXDTS was insignificant and negative while PR was found to have favorable effect on GDP in Nigeria.

Isibor, Omorose and Ahmed (2024) studied foreign capital inflows and economic growth; comparative evidence from African Anglophone and francophone countries for the period 1981 to 2022. Foreign direct investment, Foreign Portfolio Investment, Foreign Debt Stock, Personal Remittance, and Official Development Assistance were selected as the independent variables while Real Gross Domestic Product was used as the dependent variable for ten (10) African countries. Initial tests were carried out and the panel random effect estimation as selected by the Hausman test was also carried out. The result of the study revealed that Foreign Direct Investment and Foreign Portfolio Investment have negative influence on growth in both blocks in Africa but Foreign Direct Investment showed a significant influence on growth in francophone countries. The study concluded that, foreign debt stock, personal remittances and official development assistance contributed more to economic growth in countries in Africa for the period under review.

Habila, Nwakoby and Okaro (2023) examined the effect of private foreign capital on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1999 to 2021. Foreign capitals inflows indicators; foreign direct investment, foreign portfolio investment and remittances were selected as independent variables to proxy private foreign capitals and to examined their effects on gross domestic product proxy for economic growth in Nigeria. The study utilized Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag to test the data. The results showed that FDI was significant and positively related to economic growth, Remittances was significant but have negative influence on economic growth while FPI has insignificant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Bashir, (2024) investigated external debt and economic growth relationship in Nigeria for the period 1981 to 2021, using ARDL techniques to analyze the data for the study. Real interest rate, openness, external debt and domestic investment were examined to check their effects on gross domestic product proxy for economic growth in Nigeria growth. The result of the study found that there is a long run relationship among the study variables and that there is an inverse relationship between real interest rate and economic growth, the external debt impact negatively as against openness to trade and domestic investment averagely impacting positively on economic growth in both short-run and long-run.

Ariayefa, Ebimowei and Joseph, (2024) examined the impact of FDI on economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2022. Real gross domestic product was used to proxy economic growth while FDI, gross fixed capital formation, per capita income and Exchange rate EXR were selected as the explanatory variables. The study employed ARDL technique to estimate the model. The results of the study revealed that in the long run, foreign direct investment, per capita income and exchange rate were positive but statistically insignificant to economic growth in Nigeria while gross fixed capital formation was also found to be insignificant.

Onwuteaka et al (2023) examined international capital inflows and economic development of Nigeria for the period 1986 to 2021. Foreign direct investment, Foreign Portfolio Investment, External Debt Stock and Remittance were selected as the explanatory variables while Human Development Index was used as the explained variable to proxy economic development in Nigeria, using ARDL and granger causality techniques to analyze the data. The results of the study revealed that FDI, FPI, EXTD and RMT from Diaspora have no significant effect on human development index as a measure of economic development in Nigeria.

Olasehinde and Afolabi (2023) examined external debt and economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1981 to 2022. ARDL bond techniques and granger causality were used to analyze the data for the study. The result of the study revealed that there was evidence of long run relationship among the variables. Foreign reserves, external debt, Interest rate and openness were examined as the explanatory variables on GDP proxy for economic growth as the explained variable. The result of the study reported that only foreign reserves have positive and significant long run impact on gross domestic product in Nigeria.

Oke, Adegoke and Akosile (2023) examined the impact of FDI on capital market capitalization in Nigeria for the period, 1986 to 2020. The study utilized ordinary least square, Johansen co-integration and Error correction model to analyze data. The short run results revealed that all the explanatory variables except foreign direct investment maintain positive relationship with the dependent variable. The long run model revealed that only money supply was negatively related to MC while the remaining variables (foreign direct investment, Share Price Index and inflation) maintained positive relations with the explanatory variable.

Akarara and Ouseibai (2022) investigated the effect of foreign capital inflows on economic performance in Nigeria for the period 1981 to 2020. Augmented Dickey fuller unit root test, system wise Johanson cointegration test, error correction model, least square econometric techniques and granger causality test were applied to test the data. The tests result revealed a negative and negligible influence link between FDI and GDP, positive but negligible influence between Remittances, Net official assistance and GDP while government capital formation had positive and substantial influence on GDP both in the short and long-run.

Urama et al, (2022) examined the effect of foreign capital inflows on economic growth in Nigeria for the period, 1981 to 2020. Foreign direct investment, gross fixed capital formation and personal remittance were examined as the explanatory variables while real gross domestic product for the period was used as the explained variable. The study adopted the autoregressive distributed lag model to test the available data. The results of the test revealed that; FDI, GFCF and PR have strong impact on real gross domestic product in Nigeria.

Adegboye et al, (2021) examined the extent to which institutional challenges affect inflow of direct investment and its transmitting effect on economic development in 30 Sub-Saharan African countries. The analysis was conducted under the panel framework and Hausman effect test. Economic development was measured using human development index while

foreign capital inflows and institutional factors; Foreign direct investment, domestic investment, infrastructure, political stability, government effectiveness and accessibility were examined as the explanatory variables. The results of the study showed that institutional balancing is a major requirement that attract inflows of foreign capital.

Ehikioya et al, (2020) studied the dynamic aspect of external debt and economic growth in 43 African countries for the period 2001 to 2018. Johansen Co-integration test and system Generalized method of Moments (GMM) were applied to analysis the data for

study. The finding of the study showed that a long run equilibrium relationship exists between external debt and economic growth in Africa. The study further demonstrated that beyond a specific capacity, the short run converge equilibrium in the long run and external debt reflected a deteriorating impact on economic growth in African countries. Muhammed and Adamu (2020) examined the effect of external debt on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1986 to 2016. The data for study were sourced from CBN data base. Granger causality test, unit root test and Johansen co-integration test were carried out to analyze the data. The result of study revealed that there is a positive relationship between foreign direct investment, exchange rate and economic growth while external debt showed an insignificant long run relationship between real gross domestic products proxy for economic growth in Nigeria. Kisito and Hooi (2019) studied foreign capital inflows growth nexus in Nigeria for the period 1980 to 2015. The stationarity test carried out showed that there was a mixed level of stationarity which necessitated the used of auto-regressive distributive lag mechanism. The findings of the study showed that portfolio investment contributed significantly to the growth in the Nigerian economy while, foreign debt and aids reported a negative relationship with growth in the Nigerian economy for the period under review. The study concluded that, foreign aids have not provided any contribution to the growth of the economy for over a long period.

3. Methodology

This study employs the ex-post-facto research design in conjunction with econometric procedures as the data for the study were obtained from previously concluded events and are considered historical data. This research design is superior because, it usually involves more than one sample or variables, often over an extended period of time. As such, it is convenient for time series studies. This research design is extended over time which allows the researcher to examine the changes in the dependent variable in relation to the impact of the independent variables. Indicators of foreign capital inflows; foreign direct investment, foreign portfolio investment, external debt stock and foreign aids were examined on gross domestic product for the period 1981 to 2023. Therefore, all the variables employed for this study can be traced to this population with finite time length. The researcher employed the convenient sampling technique due to availability of data method to choose four (4) variables with seemingly presumed linear property over finite time dimensions. Further effort made to expand the scope of the observations so that additional variables could be admitted was stunted because of unavailability of data. The sample size for the study corresponds with the scope of the study which ranged from 1981 to 2023 and represents 42 observations.

Model Specifications

$$GDP = f(FDI, FPI, EXTDS, FAS) \text{ --- (1)}$$

$$GDP = a_0 + a_1FDI_t + a_2FPI_t + a_3EXTDS_t + a_4FAS_t + \mu \text{ --- (2)}$$

Where:

GDP = Gross domestic product = Gross domestic product is operationally measured as the total monetary value of all goods and services produced in the economy of Nigeria over the period, 1981 to 2023.

FDI = Foreign direct investment = is operationalized as the net inflow of annual official investment by multi-national corporations in tangibles assets of companies situated in Nigeria for the period, 1981 to 2023. It is measured in billions of Naira.

FPI = Foreign portfolio investment = Foreign portfolio Investment is operationally measured as the total monetary value of investments made by foreigners in financial assets of companies in the Nigerian financial market, measured in Billions of Naira to ascertain its effect on gross domestic product in the Nigerian economy.

EXTDS= External debt stock = External debt stock is operationalized as the total amount of money borrowed by the Nigerian government from other countries of the world for the period measured in Naira value.

FAS = Foreign aid= Foreign aids, in the form of Official Development Assistance (concessional loans and grants) from other nations, the total amount of concessional loans and grants inflows from other countries to the Nigerian economy is measured in Naira value for the period 1981 to 2023.

a_0 =Constant Term $a_1 - a_4$ = coefficient to Predictors

μ, ξ = Error Terms Apriori Expectations: $a_1 - a_4 > 0$

Methods of Data analysis

Descriptive statistics, Unit Root, Cointegration Test and Error Correction Model (ECM) were employed to analyze the data for the study. It has been proven that the regression of a non-stationary time series on another non-stationary time series may lead to a spurious regression. The important contribution of the concept of unit root and cointegration is to find out if regression residual is stationary. Thus, a test for co-integration enables us to avoid spurious regression situation. Johansen (1988) pointed out that a linear combination of two or more non stationary time series may be stationary, if such a stationary linear combination of two or more non- stationary time series exists, the non-stationary time series are said to be co-integrated and may be interpreted as long-run relationship among the variables.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of Foreign Capital Inflows variables and Gross Domestic Product

	GDP	FDI	FPI	EXTDS	FAS
Mean	157.5571	2.803421	30.88895	34.55684	0.746053
Median	133.9000	1.985000	20.00000	23.67500	0.525000
Maximum	489.0000	8.840000	86.63000	120.8400	4.940000
Minimum	3.900000	0.190000	3.090000	4.080000	0.110000
Std.Dev.	130.5150	2.502840	25.49283	31.66302	0.919520
Skewness	0.807839	1.055212	1.072181	0.823038	3.686718
Kurtosis	2.692013	3.022040	2.884624	2.867469	16.03139
Jarque-Bera	4.283344	7.052761	7.301703	4.317953	354.9590
Probability	0.117458	0.029411	0.025969	0.115443	0.000000
Sum	5987.170	106.5300	1173.780	1313.160	28.35000
Sum Sq.Dev.	630264.2	231.7757	24045.72	37094.22	31.28411
Observations	42	42	42	42	42

Source: Extracted from Eviews-12 and Author's Computation, 2025.

Table 4.2: Summary Compilation of Stationarity (Unit Root) Test of Employed Variables

Variable	ADF T-Statistic at Level	ADF T-Statistic at 1st Diff	1% CV	5% CV	10% CV	Probability	Order of Integration
GDP	-0.260579	-4.578579***	-3.679322	-2.967767	-2.622989	0.0006	I(1)
FDI	-0.895315	-7.354184***	-3.670170	-2.960170	-2.621007	0.0000	I(1)
FPI	-0.929257	-4.614372***	-3.752946	-2.998064	-2.638752	0.0004	I(1)
EXD	-2.110527	-5.738673***	-3.679322	-2.967767	-2.622989	0.0001	I(1)
FAS	-2.101969	-4.653304***	-3.670170	-2.963972	-2.621007	0.0009	I(1)

Source: Extracted from Eviews-12 and Author's Computation, 2025

Table 4.3: Johansen Co-integration Test

Date: 07/28/25

Time: 09:34

Sample (adjusted): 1988–2023

Included observations: 36 after adjustments

Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend

Series: GDP, FDI, FPI, EXDTS, FAS

Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None*	0.920148	238.4063	159.5297	0.0000
At most 1*	0.728659	147.4134	125.6154	0.0012
At most 2*	0.623765	100.4557	95.75366	0.0228
At most 3	0.523864	65.26425	69.81889	0.1094
At most 4	0.437182	38.55037	47.85613	0.2786
At most 5	0.291829	17.85759	29.79707	0.5767
At most 6	0.127611	5.435089	15.49471	0.7610
At most 7	0.014351	0.520392	3.841465	0.4707

Trace test indicates 3 co-integrating equation(s) at the 0.05 level.

*Denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level.

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values.

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None*	0.920148	90.99291	52.36261	0.0000
At most 1*	0.728659	46.95767	46.23142	0.0417
At most 2	0.623765	35.19148	40.07757	0.1604
At most 3	0.523864	26.71388	33.87687	0.2790
At most 4	0.437182	20.69279	27.58434	0.2952
At most 5	0.291829	12.42250	21.13162	0.5065
At most 6	0.127611	4.914697	14.26460	0.7526
At most 7	0.014351	0.520392	3.841465	0.4707

Max-Eigenvalue test indicates 2 co-integrating equation(s) at the 0.05 level.

*Denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level.

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values.

The short-run dynamic influence of foreign capital inflow indicators (Foreign Direct Investment, Foreign Portfolio Investment, External Debt Stock, Foreign Aids) on Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria is the main objective of this study. This objective is examined

along with the degree of disequilibrium that can be corrected in a year. The findings summary is presented in **Table 4.4** below.

Table 4.4 Summary of Findings

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(FDI(-1))	-6.029850	2.147319	-2.808083	0.0087
D(FPI(-1))	0.099700	0.141285	0.705665	0.4858
D(EXD(-1))	-0.136747	0.170448	-0.802276	0.4287
D(FAS(-1))	-5.589980	4.326861	-1.291925	0.2062

R-squared	0.974264	Mean dependent var	157.5571
Adjusted R-squared	0.968258	S.D. dependent var	130.5150
S.E.of regression	23.25277	Akaikein for criterion	9.315390
Sum squared resid	16220.74	Schwarz criterion	9.660145
Log likelihood	-168.9924	Hannan-Quinn criter.	9.438051
Durbin-Watson stat	1.905198		

Source: Author Computation, 2025.

Hypotheses Testing

The test is based on the t-statistic, probability value and coefficient of each independent variable. As a rule of thumb, the standard 5% significant level is the preferred decision criterion to state whether a relationship is strong/significant or weak/insignificant while the value of the coefficient tells the extent of the relationship between the correlates.

H₀₁: Foreign Direct Investment has no significant influence on Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria.

The short run dynamic results as displayed in table 4.4 shows that the coefficient of FDI is negatively signed with a probability value that is less than 0.05%. This suggests that FDI has a negative but significant relationship with GDP for the period under reviewed. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis

H₀₂: Foreign Portfolio Investment does not significantly drive Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria. The short run dynamic results displayed in table 4.4 shows that the coefficient of FPI from lag 1 is positively signed with t-statistic and probability value is greater than 0.05 significant levels. Hence there is positive and insignificant relationship between FPI and GDP in Nigeria. The result is in line with a priori expectation because of the positive correlation but not significant. We therefore, accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis.

H₀₃: External Debt Stock does not significantly impact on Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria. The results in table 4.4 show that External Debt stock display negative coefficient in lag 1 and with t-statistic and probability value higher than 0.05. Hence, there is negative and insignificant relationship between EXTDS and GDP. We therefore, accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis.

H₀₄: Foreign Aids has no significant influence on Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria. In table 4.4, Foreign Aids shows a negative coefficient in lag, with a probability value that is

higher than 0.05. Hence, there is negative and insignificant relationship between FAS and GDP. We therefore, accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis.

Discussion of Findings

As shown in table 4.4 above, FDI is negatively signed with a probability value that is less than 0.05%. This suggests that an increase in FDI will lead to a strong decrease in GDP in the short-run. Hence there is negative and significant relationship between FDI and GDP. The result does not validate apriori expectation on the ground of the negative sign. The implication is that, a unit increase in FDI decreases GDP significantly. Foreign Portfolio Investment FPI from lag 1 is positively signed with t-statistic and probability values that are higher than 0.05. This implies that an increase in FPI could result in an insignificant increase in GDP in the short-run. Hence there is positive and insignificant relationship between FPI and GDP in Nigeria. The result is in line with apriori expectation because of the positive correlation but not significantly related with the explained variable GDP. This suggest that the inflow of FPI could increase the supply of foreign exchange and reduce the foreign exchange pressure, thereby increasing the volume of investable fund in to the domestic economy that will raise the quantum of investment and the productive capacity of the domestic economy. The weak impact may be due to insufficient quantum of foreign portfolio investment that flows into the country as a result of the prevailing economic condition. External Debt stock display negative coefficient in lag 1 and with t-statistic and probability value higher than 0.05. This means that, an increase in EXTDS one year ago would lead to an insignificant decrease in GDP in the short-run while Foreign Aids shows a negative coefficient in lag 1, with a probability value that is higher than 0.05. The implication is that, increase in FAS one year ago would trigger decrease in the GDP in the short-run.

Summary of Findings

The results of the Long-Run Johansen cointegration test revealed that there is evidence of cointegrating long-run relationship among the indicators of Foreign Capital Inflows and Economic Growth in Nigeria. The short run dynamic results shows that Foreign Direct Investment at lag 1 exhibit negative and significant impact on current year Gross Domestic Product to the extent that, a 1% increase in previous year Foreign Direct Investment could lead to about -6.03% reduction in gross domestic product in the country. This is not in line with apriori expectation; the negative influence of FDI on growth may be as a result of Nigerian's inappropriate implementations of economic policies on FDI. The weak positive impact of Foreign Portfolio Investment on Gross

Domestic Product suggests that the inflow of FPI could increase the supply of foreign exchange and reduce the foreign exchange pressure, thereby increasing the volume of investable fund in to the domestic economy that will raise the quantum of investment and the productive capacity of the domestic economy. External debt stock and foreign aids for the period showed negative and insignificant influence on GDP. This implies that, increase in the inflows of external debt stock and foreign aids, instead of increasing output levels, reduces it such that, the level of goods and services in the domestic economy dwindles, hence reducing the productive capacity of the domestic economy which could be as a result of ineffective financial control system that led to funds diversion from predetermined productive economic task to non-productive activities. Conclusion The main objective of this research work is to investigate the relationship between foreign capital inflows and economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1981 to 2023. Specifically, the study examined indicators of foreign capital flows; foreign direct investment, foreign portfolio investment, external debt stock and foreign aids to test their relationship with gross domestic product proxy for economic growth in

Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that foreign direct investment is a significant predictor of economic growth in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following Recommendations are discussed and suggested for Policy Implementation

- i. Foreign direct investment proves to be a significant predictor of economic growth in Nigeria but exhibits a negative syndrome which could be as a result of poor implementation of FDI policies by the Nigerian government. The study suggests that, the managers of the Nigerian economy should consider restructuring economic policies on foreign direct investment with the aim of increasing investment inflows that is capable of improving the value of domestic production, leading to high productive capacity.
- ii. External borrowing is expected to improve the productive capacity of the nation's economy. Therefore, deliberate efforts should be made to effectively channel borrowed funds to target productive economic activities that are capable of increasing the productive capacity of the economy.
- iii. Also, proactive financial control measures should be set in place to stop diversion of funds foreign financial resources from the productive sectors to non-productive sectors of the economy.

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